

Table 3. Average number of spores produced by type 4 lesions on 4 rice varieties inoculated with 2 blast isolates and incubated for 36 and 72 hours, from counts at 4 inoculation intervals.

Days after inoculation	Spores (no./m × 1000)											
	Isolate 2017						Isolate 7506					
	Tetep		KTH		IR442		IR36		KTH		IR442	
	36 h	72 h	36 h	72 h	36 h	72 h	36 h	72 h	36 h	72 h	36 h	72 h
6	0.60	0.40	0.02	0.08	0.26	0.28	2.90	1.06	3.28	2.16	1.06	0.54
7	0.28	0.14	0.78	1.02	0.46	0.06	–	–	–	–	–	–
10	0.04	0.10	0.30	0.44	0.28	0.58	–	–	3.48	3.44	1.46	1.28
19	0.24	0.42	0.68	0.36	–	–	–	–	1.22	0.40	0.30	0.81

isolates (Table 1). IR36 had fewer and smaller lesions than IR442 and KTH, indicating that number of lesions and size of lesions may be components of horizontal resistance to rice blast

(Table 1, 2). The variety had no effect on spore production of either isolate of the blast fungus, indicating that sporulation capacity is not a component of horizontal resistance, but is a

reproductive function of the blast fungus. That is further supported by the fact that lesion size did not affect the number of spores per lesion (Table 3).

Reaction of indica and japonica rices to blast in Taiwan

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Five uniform blast nurseries were established yearly from 1974 to 1978 to test rice varieties and selections from various breeding stations for blast reaction in Taiwan. Four were on the western coast (Yilan, Nantou, Chiayi, Pingtung) and one in the east (Taitung). The program was jointly conducted by the Taipei, Taichung, Chiayi, Kaohsiung,

and Taitung stations with the assistance of the Joint Commission on Rural Reconstruction.

Among the 693 entries were 499 japonicas and 194 indicas. Thirty-four percent of the entries showed resistance to leaf blast; 55%, to neck blast. Fifteen and 48% of the japonicas and 75 and 84% of the indicas were resistant to leaf and neck blast, respectively. Japonica varieties generally appear more sensitive to leaf blast; indicas have more overall blast resistance than japonicas under local conditions.

A positive relationship existed between leaf and neck blast reactions (correlation coefficients were 0.77 for

japonicas, 0.64 for indicas, and 0.79 when pooled). All correlations were significant at the 1% level indicating varieties resistant to leaf blast were resistant to neck blast, but a smaller *r* value for indicas may lead to exceptions.

Of 35 varieties being commercially produced (28 japonicas, 7 indicas), only 8 (3 japonicas, 5 indicas) were resistant to both neck and leaf blast. Among the susceptible were two leading varieties, Tainan 5 and Tainung 67; the two were planted on 384,000 ha in 1978 (51% of Taiwan's total planted areas). Chianung 242, until recently one of Taiwan's most popular resistant cultivars, was also susceptible. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

Comparison of oxalic acid concentration in rice varieties resistant and susceptible to the brown planthopper

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Resistance to the brown planthopper (BPH) in certain rice varieties is mainly governed by chemicals in the phloem tissues that inhibit sucking. To test oxalic

acid for its potential in inhibiting sucking by BPH, we isolated it from leaf sheath extracts of Mudgo, a resistant variety. We compared the oxalic acid concentration in the following 28 rice varieties, with special reference to differences in their varietal resistance to BPH.

- Susceptible varieties: IR8, IR20, IR22, IR24, TN1
- Resistant varieties with:
Bph 1 gene – IR26, IR32058-78, Mudgo, CO 10, MTU15
Bph 2 gene – IR32, H5, H105,

CR94-13, ASD7

Bph 3 gene – Kuruhondarwala, Gangala, Rathu Heenati

Bph 4 gene – Heenhoranamawee, Babawee, Lekam Samba, Kalukuruwee, Kahata Samba

Unknown gene(s) – PTB21, PTB33, Sudu Hondarwala, Sinna Sivappu, Balamawee

Organic acids were separated from 70% EtOH extracts of fresh leaf sheaths from 40-day-old plants using ion exchange chromatography through Amberlite CG120 and Amberlite